

IMPROVING THE SPIRIT OF YOUTH THE ROLE OF ART AND CULTURE IN THE ORGANIZATION OF THEIR LEISURE

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada yoshlarning bo'sh vaqtini mazmunli tashkil etish orqali ularning ma'naviyatini yuksaltirishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari O'zbekiston davlat san'at va madaniyat instituti misolida yozilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *madaniyat, ma'naviyat, ma'rifat, ijtimoiy tabaqa, sotsiologik tadqiqotlar, vatan taraqqiyoti, zamonaviy tendensiya, besh muhim tashabbus.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье описаны современные тенденции поднятия морального духа молодежи посредством содержательной организации досуга на примере Узбекского государственного института искусств и культуры.*

Ключевые слова: *культура, духовность, просвещение, социальный класс, социологические исследования, национальное развитие, современные тенденции, пять важных инициатив.*

Annotation: *This article describes the current trends in raising the morale of young people through the meaningful organization of leisure time on the example of the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture.*

Key words: *culture, spirituality, enlightenment, social class, sociological research, national development, modern trends, five important initiatives.*

Spirituality is not something that is frozen. It improves, enriches and changes with society and man, with social practice. It is influenced in some way by public policy, social classes, nations, peoples, countries, cultures. Spiritual values are not assimilated, valued and understood in the same way by different social classes, strata and groups. Sociological research will be needed to study these issues. This means that the "fundamentals of spirituality" are also connected with the science of sociology, using its methods and conclusions.

The whole process of the development of society and its attainment to the present level can be called the history of the constant growth of freedom, humanity, or the history of the formation and development of the spiritual personality.

The importance of spirituality for national revival, strengthening independence, and enriching the minds of the people requires that it be studied in its entirety and that its social functions, opportunities, and potential be revealed.

Only clear and relatively perfect ideas about spirituality will allow us to effectively use spiritual factors in strengthening the independence of our country.

Today there is a need not only to bring together the issues of spirituality, but also to study them in terms of a single subject. In addition, our period is the period of the emergence of new sciences in the junction of different disciplines.

The Fundamentals of Spirituality deals with almost all the social sciences and humanities. It is closely related to theology as well as to the philosophical sciences. Therefore, it is impossible not to refer to religious materials in the study of the origins, stages of development and laws of spirituality.

Spirituality was also developed in the first secular cultural creative activity of man. It has always been that way, and it is still that way. The impact of secular activities on spirituality is often overlooked in religious studies. The conclusion is that the "Fundamentals of Spirituality" studies the sciences of folklore and literature, linguistics, cultural studies in the broadest sense, history, social psychology, enriches them, complements them in the direction of its subject, and enriches.

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The impact of public policy, ideological struggle or cooperation between states, and international cultural relations on the spiritual process is difficult to understand without the help of political science.

Finally, the subject "Fundamentals of Spirituality" aims not only to understand a large group of social phenomena, not only in the narrow educational tasks, but also to contribute to the education of a harmoniously developed generation of independent Uzbekistan. He said. This requires that the discipline of pedagogy and the science of pedagogical psychology communicate.

The study of the subject of "Fundamentals of Spirituality" not only enriches and expands our worldview, but also enhances our ability to consciously participate in social processes, to educate young people in the spirit of high spirituality. It is necessary not only for future educators, teachers, but also for all professionals - journalists, writers, artists, scientists, managers, engineers, organizers and others.

The emergence of an independent discipline called "Fundamentals of Spirituality" also stems from the development needs of Islam Karimov. In order to have a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of social development in general, this science is very much needed today. The subject of "Fundamentals of Spirituality" is as universal as any other discipline. It would be fair to say that the need for it as a separate science was first recognized in Uzbekistan and included in the curriculum as a contribution to the development of modern science in our country. Today, state standards, textbooks and textbooks are being developed in this subject.

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In the process of spirituality formation, the original human nature began to take shape in man, and he gradually became a spiritual person.

The savage is not a spiritual being, so he is not free. He is completely dependent on nature, its coincidences and whims. The "freedom" of the savage is based on instinct. Spiritual freedom is based on moral, legal and economic norms, free choice. Unlike the savage, the primitive man has elements of a spiritual personality. However, he is not yet a spiritual person because he lacks individuality and responsibility. The elements of spirituality in primitive man are part of the collective consciousness, the will, and not the manifestations of the independent individual consciousness and will.

The main goal of spiritual development is to cultivate a spiritual personality. A spiritual person is one who is free to think and to choose freely. Only conscious, voluntary obedience to conscious choice, an

understanding of social necessity, and the creation of legal, moral, and economic norms that serve humanity and development can give a person freedom and spirituality.

As mentioned above, spirituality is a combination of human kindness, justice, righteousness, integrity, conscience, honor, patriotism, love of beauty, enjoyment of it, hatred of evil, will, perseverance, and so on. It is an integral unity, a common set of original human qualities and attributes. Spirituality is not just a set of human qualities, but also a set of positive qualities.

An important factor in shaping the spirituality of young people is the education system. Science and education should be considered as a basic condition for human development and the development of the nation. That is why our Constitution stipulates that schools and the education of young people be under the control of the state.

The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov in his book "High spirituality is an invincible force" described the contribution of schools and teachers in the development of society. "The work of teachers and coaches, who decide the future not only of our youth, but of our entire nation, cannot be measured or compared to anything."

Focusing on the education of young people from the earliest days of our state independence, the upbringing of a physically healthy and spiritually mature generation has been identified as a priority, and it has risen to the level of public policy. The State programs called Mother and Child, Youth, Harmoniously Developed Generation, Family, Year of Prosperous Life and their implementation are an expression of the noble aspirations of our people for a bright future. The programs set the task of forming a harmoniously developed generation that is physically and spiritually healthy, independent-minded, has a scientific and modern outlook, deep knowledge, a sense of patriotism and nationalism.

As you know, the process of globalization is entering our lives quickly and deeply. Globalization is, first, in the process of unprecedented acceleration of life, the strengthening of various integration and cooperation between countries, the rapid spread of modern information technologies and scientific achievements, the acquisition of a new quality of dialogue between peoples, opportunities for cooperation. This is a positive aspect of globalization, but another aspect of the globalization process today is that it is becoming a weapon of ideological influence on young people, as well as a battleground for various political and ideological forces. "Today, ideological landfills are more powerful than

nuclear landfills," said the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov. That is why the education of young people has always been in the center of our state's attention, and this process has been going on continuously during the years of independence. In general, all the laws on youth adopted in our country, along with a thorough education, ensure the active participation and participation of our youth in the international arena, socio-economic protection of minors, orphans, large families, identification and development of talented youth. Issues such as lab support are under constant scrutiny. It is noteworthy that in our country, special attention, kindness and care are paid to children deprived of parental care and upbringing. In 2015-2017, the issues of gradual strengthening of the material and technical base of orphanages, boarding schools and preschool institutions, radical improvement of the educational process have been identified. The role of the community and the public in educating young people is great.

It should be noted that the role of elders and enlightened fathers and mothers is important for our young men and women to enter the independent life, for young families to find their place, for the formation of kindness and goodwill among people. Parental responsibility plays a special role in the spiritual upbringing of young people. The purest and purest feelings of man, the notions of life for the first time, worldviews, goodness and virtue, nobility and kindness, sacred concepts necessary for man, such as honor, andisha, begin to be decided in the family first and then moves to the community.

Important tools for education to fully meet the spiritual needs of young people: the press, television, cinema, theater, literature, music, painting and sculpture, the Internet of the media, the human heart and mind in general it will be necessary to raise all areas that can have a direct impact to a new level of quality. At the same time, it is necessary to quickly eliminate the existing shortcomings, both large and small, in these areas and get rid of such negative situations.

The importance of philosophical, social, political and humanitarian sciences in the spiritual education of young people in our country is invaluable, so the representatives of these sciences will have to fulfill their responsibilities at the level of today's requirements. Textbooks, manuals, literature and specialists in this field are required.

From the above, we can conclude that our people, especially our youth, must always be vigilant, vigilant and vigilant in order to strengthen the spiritual world and maintain its inviolability, to conduct a well thought

out, scientifically based and continuous spiritual education against threats. Will be required. The first initiative is to increase the interest of young people in music, painting, literature, theater and other arts, to reveal their talents. Conducted.

The Institute has published books of poetry of students who won the creative competition "Muhammad Yusuf - followers of Muhammad Yusuf" based on the poems of Muhammad Yusuf "Muhammad Yusuf - Homeland singer" and the concert program was widely broadcast on Uzbek television and radio. . The institute also has several clubs for students to spend their free time effectively and meaningfully. These include "The languages and art", "Young translators", "Piano", "Computer graphics and design", "The art of dubbing", "Creative management", "Design", "World of art and culture", "E Students are involved in such clubs as "zoz", "Doira", "Electronic chess".

At the same time, in their free time, students can take trips to museums, cinemas, and other places of interest in our city, such as the Alley of Writers.

In addition, performances and charity concerts with the participation of students of preschool institutions, orphanages, special boarding schools for children with disabilities, secondary schools and nursing homes with the participation of students aimed at raising the morale of people and youth.

He graduated from the institute with a master's and bachelor's degree in faculties and departments, educational theater, sports complexes and other departments.

There is a wide range of opportunities for 22 students to start work and improve the lessons of office work in the state language, as well as students are attached to theaters, museums, cinemas, cultural and recreational facilities and other institutions located in the capital.

There was also a large banner with the name "Muhammad Yusuf - the singer of the homeland", as well as one of the central pavilions in the courtyard of the institute, named after the poet, created two paintings by the poet.

The Department of National Singing of the Institute held a competition of songs with the participation of Muhammad Yusuf's poems, and an exhibition of paintings by Muhammad Yusuf was held at the Academic Theater of the Institute. The poet's wife Nazira As-Salam also took part in it.

In addition, a 3-8 classroom on the third floor of the main building of the institute has a classroom named after Muhammad Yusuf.

In addition, in February 2021 in the building of the Academic Theater of the Institute was held a large concert program with songs based on the

poems of Muhammad Yusuf with the participation of famous singers and artists, which was widely broadcast on Uzbek television and radio. is being illuminated.

This academic year and regular events dedicated to the life and work of the poet, the work carried out in the "Alley of Writers", all activities related to the life of the poet on television and radio, on the official website of the institute, as well as It is widely disseminated on the Uzbek national information portals on the Internet.

In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6108 of November 6, 2020 "On measures to develop education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan" and Uzbekistan 6 schools of Zangiota district of Tashkent region, as well as 6 schools of the Tashkent region 15 mahallas of Tashkent have been attached and a memorandum of cooperation has been signed between the schools.

A spiritual and educational event was organized in accordance with the agreements set out in the memorandum. As part of five important initiatives put forward by the President, the professors and teachers of the institute have so far held master classes and competitions for more than 15 talented students.

The department of Uzbek language and literature of the institute has signed cooperation agreements with the Abdulla Qodiri School of Creativity, the Muhammad Yusuf School of Creativity in Andijan region and the state secondary schools specializing in philology in Tashkent.

In particular, on December 25, 2021, a scientific-practical event on "The image of Abdullah Qadiri in the works of Muhammad Yusuf" was organized.

This year at the secondary school specializing in philology

On January 6, an event entitled "Muhammad Yusuf and Abdulla Aripov - the tradition of teacher-student" was held.

At the same time, the teachers of the department conducted trainings in these educational institutions. In order to instill in students a sense of respect for the history of the country and national values, the contest "My country is my pride", "The most active educated readers", a spiritual and educational meeting on "Court and youth", Reading evening on the theme "My dear Uzbekistan, live forever", "Information and educational hours", "The book is my friend", "The book I read", "Student reader" reading nights and contests were organized. The number of fiction books has been increased to 492, the number of textbooks to 867, and the number of other types of literature to 110 in the library established in the dormitory No. 1.

The number of fiction books has been increased to 1,103, the number of textbooks to 1,824, and the number of other types of literature to 292 in the library established in the dormitory No. 2.

“Ancient and dear Navruz!” As part of the festive event, the competition "The most active reader" was held among faculty, staff and students. The event also included competitions for "Best Foreign Article Writer", "Best Foreign Newspaper Author", and "Best Article Published in Journales Recognized by the HAC".

The fifth initiative includes more than 25 events involving more than 850 young people. On February 24, 2021, meetings were held with the participation of experts in the field of “Girls' Circle” competition, “Protection of women from oppression and violence.”

The institute also held a competition "Spring Meals" for students living in TTJ, and in March 2021, competitions such as “Ball Girls”.

A separate sewing room has been set up in the dormitory to provide vocational training for students in their spare time and the necessary equipment and sewing machines have been provided.

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